

Merging BSP based swarm dynamics and distributed ledger technologies for smart marine infrastructures

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Abstract: Distributed ledger technologies, together with AI, smart systems and robotics could provide a scalable and robust platform for the smart underwater and surface marine infrastructures of the close future. They will be harbours or ports, marine farms or remote tourism facilities - only accessible through robotic avatars - for protected areas or for the elders. Autonomous Marine Vehicles, IoT networks, and humans will coexist in highly heterogeneous multivendor multiplatform environments where market transactions and complex administrative procedures will be ubiquitous. Some blockchains such as the Ethereum network are able to provide distributed scalable computing and trustable functionalities, capable of managing both technical interactions and market transactions among very diversified autonomous agents. For these reasons they seem to provide a valuable backbone for the smart marine infrastructure of the coming decades. In this paper we outline our research and innovation strategy and present our results showing the potential benefits of a subsidiary architecture integrating distributed ledger technologies with swarms of autonomous surface robots implemented by a Belief Space Planning approach.

Keywords: Smart Marine Facilities, Blockchain, Ethereum, Multi agent systems, BSP, Swarms

1. INTRODUCTION

The concurrent great progress in Internet of Things, Machine Learning and AI has triggered a new industrial revolution, dubbed Industry 4.0 in Germany and Italy, Smart Factory in the US and Digitalization of European Industry at European level. The massive availability of computing power, cheap sensors and smart systems, big data and AI agents has opened tremendous opportunities not only to radically redesign factories and supply chains, but also our cities and their surrounding territories. This has led to the idea of ‘Smart Cities’ and ‘Smart Lands’ (large urban sprawls digitally connected in such a way to create a kind of ‘virtual city’). It is natural to extend the smart city and smart land paradigms to complex marine surface and underwater socio-economic and infrastructure systems like ports, marine farms, large monitoring and surveillance systems and, last but not least, remote tourism facilities, protected areas only accessible by robotic avatars or where avatars are provided to allow the fruition by elders or impaired people, see XPrize (2022). The expected population growth and likely sea level rise will raise the importance of the sustainable and regenerative exploitation of sea and ocean resources. Robotics and AI are key enabling technologies to materially expand the reach of human action in terms of distance from the coasts, underwater depth,

marine weather and latitude. This will require significant advancements. The current paradigm for smart cities and lands is based on centralised ‘cloud robotics’ architectures; all the data of the ‘smart’ city are stored and processed on huge ‘server farms’. Those architectures will possibly have scaling problems to be able to fluently manage millions or even hundred of millions of intelligent devices. Moreover the centralization of citizen data on a few mega platforms (such as those provided by Amazon, Google, Microsoft and the likes) rises privacy and political concerns. The distributed computing and data storage capabilities provided by the distributed ledger platforms may provide much needed solutions.

2. SMART MARINE FACILITIES

There are many different surface and underwater facilities that could benefit from a technology providing a secure access to resources, trustable collection of data, easier management of infrastructure and so on. In fact, ports, marinas, marine farms or remote touristic facilities, to name but a few, are now becoming accessible through suitable devices and methodologies though there are not yet protocols able to ensure security and trust; the combination of distributed ledger technologies, AI and smart team of cooperating robots could be able to fill this gap. Some current projects are trying to take a first step

forward in this direction, through the exploitation of smart robots in different context; the first example is the BlueRoSES project (2021a), aiming at creating innovative services for leisure boats and marinas, and ‘augmenting’ them with a new dimension to attract increasing interest from a diversified audience. In particular, it is foreseen that the integration of IoT and robotic technology will allow general public (the elderly and young people alike) to visit underwater sites by piloting a Remotely Operating Vehicle (ROV) from a leisure boat, a ground control room or through a web-based app. The developed technology could also be exploited with other objectives, such as enabling to address environmental challenges through the monitoring of water, seabeds and yacht hulls for safety, refitting and dismantling.

Underwater monitoring and surveillance sectors are also involved in the INNOVAMARE project (2021b), in charge of establishing an innovative ecosystem model in the area of underwater robotics and sensors with a particular focus oriented on sustainability.

Finally, a scalable automated system (including AI-driven robots and co-powered with renewable energy and second generation fuel) is foreseen in the MAELSTROM project (2021c), with the main purpose of providing diversified solutions to the complex question to the removal and sustainable treatment of marine litter.

These on-going projects show the need to apply new concepts and technologies to the marine domain to enable effective and reliable applications to the real surface and underwater infrastructures envisioned for the close future. Exploitation of blockchain services would well fit the needs of ports and marinas, for facilities inspection and maintenance, water sampling, bathymetry surveys and security assessment, and so on. Within such environmental context, the use of blockchain is straightforward, since in port areas the access to internet is usually easy through 4G and increasingly 5G technologies. Blockchain interactions with certifying third parties over the internet could then occur in real-time without particular problems.

The underwater environments raise some technical challenges: the availability of internet in underwater applications is still very limited (even if some efforts were already directed towards the establishment of the so called ‘*Internet of Underwater Things (IoUT)*’ Domingo (2012); Liou et al. (2018)) and requires further research. However, there are at least two possible ways to introduce blockchain services in underwater applications: i) make the distributed ledger technology to run locally on each robot of the cooperative team as long as it is working in an underwater mission, and then align with the internet once it emerges; ii) exploit the mentioned IoUT to connect underwater robots, allowing them to directly interact with certifying third parties and to implement the blockchain underwater.

These solutions need research and testing applications, being the second one more complex but also more desirable. Despite that, they indicate a feasible development path. This underwater scenario would enable the exploitation of robotic teams, smart systems and AI in a wide range of applications: from inspection and maintenance of underwater (deep) infrastructures, to the establishment of new infrastructures with a persistent robotic presence, to water column and seabed sampling, resource exploitation and

underwater mining, to name but a few. The same robotics, smart systems and AI technologies can be more easily exploited in surface applications, for which some difficulties are relaxed (e.g. the possibility to directly conduct transactions on the blockchain through an Internet connection). Application surface scenarios concern the port operation management and the assessment of port water quality (e.g. measurement and sampling of pollutant spilled in water by ships and other vehicles passing through the port for their operations).

These are only some of the main examples of marine and underwater facilities that would strongly benefit from the integration of distributed ledger technologies on-board the robots, augmenting their already consolidated capabilities with distributed scalable computing and trustable functionalities. Our lab aims to develop, within the next decade, robust, secure and scalable solutions for the ‘smart marine infrastructures’ based on AI, IoT, Robotics and distributed ledger technologies.

In this paper we:

- (1) describe our vision and strategy about smart marine infrastructures
- (2) provide some initial results focusing on the specific problem of merging in an subsidiary effective and efficient way distributed ledger technologies with swarm behaviours implemented by means of a BSP approach

We believe that both our vision about ‘smart marine infrastructures’ and our results about the integration of a peculiar approach to swarm management based on the BSP with blockchain technologies can be interesting for the reader. In the following section 3 we describe, as an example, the Ethereum blockchain. Any blockchain allowing to attach a ‘program’ to a secure transaction could play the same role in our system architecture. In section 4 we describe in more detail our vision of the future of smart marine infrastructures. In 5 we discuss our simulation experiments and results about our proposed subsidiary integration of blockchain technologies with small swarm of robots inspired by Reynolds’ boids and based on a belief space planning approach. We then discuss the results in section 6 and draw some conclusions and describe our future work in 7.

3. THE ETHEREUM BLOCKCHAIN

The main services provided by the Ethereum network, see Buterin (2013), are distributed secure transaction management, computing and data storage. The Ethereum network is based on a blockchain protocol. All transactions are sequentially stored in a ever growing linked chain - a ‘Merkle’ or ‘Hash Tree’, see Merkle (1982) accessible to all the nodes (computers) of the network. Those transactions are stored in ‘blocks’ protected by a tree of cryptographic hash. All transactions are anonymously known and validated by all nodes, which compete to generate the new coding hashes by executing as fast as possible a complex mathematical algorithm (the ‘proof-of-work’) and get paid in ‘gas’, a tiny fraction of the network currency, the ‘ether’. The typical characteristics of blockchains also known as ‘distributed ledgers’ is their capability to provide a secure ledger of verified transactions (kind of notary process) in a totally distributed and automated fashion

with no third parties (such as notaries, banks or credit card companies) and inherently protecting the private data of the entities (humans or machines) involved in the transactions. Ethereum has an additional very useful feature: the possibility to attach executable code to the transactions. This allows to execute in a fully automated way ‘smart contracts’. As a consequence on Ethereum or any similar networks it is possible to implement a fully distributed computing, data storage and secure transaction management and certification platform, capable to manage complex interactions, including market transactions and related mechanisms, execute programs and activate and govern robotics and automation systems. While it is possible to build a large number of networks based on those principles, it is also possible to build ‘chains’ acting as interfaces among different blockchains, creating ‘chains of chains’, such as Polkadot, Wood (2016). The distributed ledger technologies implementing the capability to execute programs and contracts in the form of programs provide an ideal platform for the smart complex infrastructures that we are envisioning, see Kapitonov et al. (2019).

4. HETEROGENEOUS MARINE MULTI-AGENT SYSTEMS APPLICATIONS

Multi-agent systems represent a great innovation and advancement in many robotics fields, above all in those that deal with harsh and hostile environments, such as space and marine applications, particularly underwater. In spite of many research activities being conducted on the topic, the problem is very far to be solved, due to the complexity of required tasks, high level of needed autonomy, dynamic changing hostile environments and so on.

Many applications could highly benefit from advancements in the field: attempts to apply cooperative multi-agent systems have been made in different contexts, from marine environment monitoring Lončar et al. (2019); Shkurti et al. (2012), to oil spill surveys and chemical pollution Vasiljevic et al. (2015); Li et al. (2017), and underwater search and rescue in natural disaster scenarios Murphy et al. (2012), this last performed by autonomous robots in charge of rough preliminary identify areas of interest to be later investigated by teleoperated vehicles. Being the topic highly complex and multifaceted, each of the cited works stresses a particular aspect. Communication is the main focus of the first two works: Lončar et al. (2019) discusses the importance of inter-robot communication to obtain a distributed monitoring by collaborative behaviour, while Shkurti et al. (2012) needs communication capabilities to allow biologists to remotely guide the system, exploiting it for ecosystems inspection applications. On the other hand, research in Vasiljevic et al. (2015), Li et al. (2017) and Murphy et al. (2012) focuses on some of the main skills and functionalities that a multi-agent robotic team should own to be effective at field: strong and redundant sensing, perceiving and predicting capabilities in the first one, understanding of exchange information and uncertainty reasoning skills in the second, coordination and capability to cover large areas effectively in the last one. Discussion about other capabilities which are mandatory for an effective marine multi-agent team is presented in Yuan et al. (2017) where the concept of formation learning is introduced, even if in a simplified robotic team context,

and in Yadegar and Meskin (2021) that reports on fault-tolerant control to ensure robustness and reliability to the system. Cooperative control strategies are addressed in Enayat and Khorasani (2017) and Mazdin et al. (2016), which both use a consensus protocol to produce the desired trajectories for each agent, and to enable the system to autonomously detect failures in measurements, respectively. The discussed aspects and control strategies reported in all the last four papers are extremely interesting; however, all of them validated results only in simulation. If, on one side, simulation is a remarkable tool to steer control design and implementation, and to speed up research by validating methodologies before going at field, on the other side experimental validation and reproducibility are mandatory to fill the gap between lab research and real applications, above all in a hostile and harsh context as the marine environment.

The central concept being pursued in all multi-agent teams of marine robots is *heterogeneity* in terms of both capabilities and structures or operative domains (underwater, surface, aerial...), even if this is still an open problem object of frontier research. Indeed, such heterogeneity would, on one hand, lend robotic team more flexibility and capability to execute complex missions; on the other, it highly increases complexity and impair currently used control methodologies.

A brand-new fleet of surface vessels is presented in Wang et al. (2021), which demonstrates the possibility to develop a cloud-based mission control architecture and thus obtain flexibility and remote access in a number of applications related to the exploration and exploitation of ocean resources. If, on one side, the premise is very interesting, on the other, the work is still at its very beginning and is simplified by the choice to employ only homogeneous surface vehicles. This strongly limits, as already discussed, the applicability and the complexity of the executable missions but, on the other hand, eases the cooperation and control design.

The possible application of blockchain technologies to robotic swarms is described in Castelló Ferrer (2019), where some raising issues such as scalability, latency and delays are mentioned. From that, few works addressing the combination of blockchain and robot swarms have been presented, such as Singh et al. (2020) and Pacheco et al. (2022), which describe applications in cooperative decision making oriented to search and rescue and swarm foraging, respectively. Research in Castelló Ferrer et al. (2021) focuses on the possibility to separate data verification from data itself. Finally, some possible solutions to the mentioned limitations are provided in Strobel et al. (2020), while Tran et al. (2019) proposes a method to manage the network partitioning possibly occurring during swarm operations. Integrating distributed ledger technologies into smart cooperative heterogeneous robotics systems would introduce significant benefits in terms of both executable applications (e.g. secure and certified data collection and sampling) and quality of execution (e.g. high processing capabilities, robustness and reliability); moreover it would increase system interoperability, by allowing effective cooperation of heterogeneous robots in actual real-world scenarios. Such distributed ledger technology already demonstrated to be effective in a trustable water monitoring scenario Berman et al. (2020), where coordination among

a leading vessel relying on blockchain and a swarm of autonomous robots was demonstrated. In that context, many results were obtained through distributed ledger technology, among which: i) once collected, data cannot be changed and remain available for further verification; ii) in the digital signature associated with data there is the time of the collected measure; iii) the system is easy to be scaled, independently of the structure or measurement sensors on-board the new vehicles. The need for the automation of economical and societal processes is, in the marine environment, even more important than it is on land. The necessity to organize the sustainable exploitation of the coastal waters as far away and as deep as possible requires a massive utilization of robotic and automation systems, fully exploiting current and future AI technologies. The complexity of the transformation and monitoring economic and societal processes occurring within the future marine infrastructures will rival those of future smart cities and lands. There will be, yet, a key difference: as many environments will be not suitable for human operation, the level of automation will have to be much higher. We will need adaptive infrastructures consisting of hundreds of thousands of robots, AIs and smart systems, if not millions or more. Those embodied and dis-embodied agents will have complex patterns and processes of interaction, complying with complex societal and legal rules and implementing planning procedures and sophisticated market interactions. We will have complex highly distributed multi-agent environments connecting a myriad AI, smart and robotics systems and humans through a scalable number of interconnected blockchains, which will mediate complex meaningful machine-to-machine and machine-to-human interactions. Those environments will need heterogeneous multi vendor multi technology platform architectures like a distributed ledger technologies integrated with robotics, automation and AI.

5. MERGING THE BLOCKCHAIN WITH SWARMS BASED ON BSP

Current distributed ledger technology implementations are too slow to allow to manage every robots in the swarm. For this reason, it is interesting to explore the feasibility of a ‘subsidiary’ control architecture where a ‘leading’ agent interface with the blockchain and collect and dispatch information from and to a smaller network of following robots. In this work we simulated a network architecture where the small network keep the formation around the leading vehicle by a mechanism implementing Reynolds’ boids model by means of an implementation of Belief Space Planning interacting with Artificial Potential Fields. In the following we describe three different scenarios of growing complexity. All of them assume that the ‘leading’ vehicle interacts with the blockchain and dispatch the orders and receive the data from a small networks of vehicles that it coordinates.

5.1 Example 1: A simple swarm application for secure fresh water monitoring

The potential of blockchain technology applied to water monitoring and quality assessment is exemplified in Berman et al. (2020), where a highly trustable environmental monitoring system is developed. In particular, a

swarm of small-sized marine vessels equipped with compact sensors is employed with different formations and number of robot companions. Such swarm supports a master autonomous ship, that is in charge of the water quality certification. This last process is achieved through the blockchain, integrating the Robonomics platform that guarantees that any third party can not alter the taken samples. The deployment of a secure sample certification and logging platform based on the blockchain with a small-sized swarm of autonomous vessels performing maneuvers allows to efficiently measure chemical parameters of water in automatic mode, exploiting the coordination of a leader-follower framework of small platoon of robots. The swarm is based on Belief Space Planning (BSP), a stochastic control methodology able to concurrently reduce the system uncertainty (model inaccuracies, environmental disturbance, measurement errors. . .) while driving the system to the reference goal. For details on this control scheme, the interested reader can refer to Platt Jr et al. (2010). Each vehicle, knowing the master ship reference path, is in charge of computing the appropriate motion for itself, exploiting the cited BSP control scheme. The formation is maintained through the implementation of the following additional rules: i) *separation*, to avoid crowding and collisions; ii) *alignment*, to keep the formation desired heading; and iii) *cohesion*, to keep the formation close to the reference path. Two different formations have been tested: ‘rhomboid’ and ‘double rhomboid’ with respectively 4 and 8 robots. The swarm tests have been performed in a mixed-reality simulation setting, while the trajectory of the leader has been obtained through field tests. Noise with different magnitudes was injected in the swarm system in order to evaluate its stability and reliability to environmental disturbance. See Berman et al. (2020) for details.

5.2 Example 2: Shaping swarm interaction with the environment

The rhomboid 4-robot formation has been employed to test the system robustness in two different environmental scenarios, respectively including one or two obstacles to be avoided. Each vehicle in the swarm was controlled through the already mentioned BSP algorithm integrated with the swarming rules listed above. A simple Artificial Potential Field (APF) technique was introduced to model the obstacles: each of them is associated to a repulsive field centered in the obstacle center and having two main parameters: r and s , respectively representing the obstacle radius and its range of influence, decreasing as the vehicle distance from the obstacle increases. In the first one-obstacle case, the employed parameters are $r = 4\text{ m}$ and $s = 5\text{ m}$; the vehicles are forced to circumvent the obstacle since it is right in the middle of the leader reference path, exerting a strong repulsive force on each robot companion. The behaviour of robots at the two side of the leader path is more or less symmetrical, since the obstacle is centered on the path itself and repulsive forces exerted on the different vehicles are comparable. In the second scenario, including obstacles at the two sides of the leader path, the employed parameters are: $r_L = 10\text{ m}$ and $s_L = 20\text{ m}$ for the obstacle on the left, and $r_R = 5\text{ m}$ and $s_R = 15\text{ m}$ for the one on the right. These two obstacles exert a force on the vehicles that pushes them closer to the leader reference path, creating a sort of bottleneck as long as the robots

Fig. 1. Path planned and executed by a swarm of 4 companion robots while avoiding two obstacles (yellow) placed on the two side of the master reference path. The combination of BSP and APF allows the robots to avoid the obstacles, inducing a motion closer to the path for the time needed to circumvent the obstacles.

are in proximity of the obstacles. Still, the system is able to avoid any collisions thanks to the integrated rules. The generated path in this second two-obstacle case is showed in Figure 1.

5.3 Example 3: Shaping swarm interaction in a context of complex access regulations

The exploitation of marine (and not only) resources can be subject to access regulation that can be different from agent to agent. Consider, for example the case of a swarm made up of 1 leader and 4 followers, all cooperating; since some areas (e.g. within a port) have a restricted access (e.g. large vehicles cannot access narrow areas, where operations are allowed only to small-sized and/or highly maneuverable vehicles), each follower is endowed with a specific authorization level, among three different ones (low, medium, high – L, M, H). The same framework can be applied to a robotic swarm in charge of sampling and assessing water quality (e.g. against pollutants) in a port environment, after big ships performed their operations. In this case, the blockchain technology can manage the access and certify the correctness of all the operations, securely dispatching and collecting all the information (these collected samples become then immutable; this can be important for instance within the pollutant tracking context: if a big ship or some company is spilling pollutants in the sea, this situation can be detected, faced and eventual actions taken). The blockchain can supervise all the (port) operations performed by the swarm and assign the authorization level of each agent. Figure 2 shows a simulation about this access regulation capability. Note that followers V2 and V4 must avoid all the restricted areas (represented by pink and light blue circles), V1 can cross light blue areas only, while V3 is allowed in all areas. All the followers, while obeying access regulation rules, should try their best to follow the leader vehicle (represented by the dash blue line).

The system should be managed in a flexible manner: since the considered environment (e.g. a port) is highly dynamic and subject to changes in conditions, the swarm should be able to react to those changes adopting alternative behaviors that can optimize the overall operation performance. Hence the swarm-supervising blockchain, during an oper-

Fig. 2. Path planned and executed by a swarm of 4 companion robots following 1 leader around a reference desired path, and obeying to the access rules imposed by the blockchain in the working area. The light blue circles represents areas in which only low-authorization vehicles are prohibited, in pink circles only high-authorization vehicles are allowed, while the rest of the area (light green) is open to all kind of vehicles. V3 can cross all areas while straight following the reference path, where as V2, being the lowest priority vehicle in the swarm, must avoid all the circles (both pink and blue) while still doing its best to follow the desired path.

ation execution, could decide that the authorization levels of some or all vehicles must change. This could be useful in different cases, such as whenever facing a failure in one of the swarm agent or if the blockchain is managing operations such as ship container loading/unloading. In this last situation, indeed, it could be more beneficial to revise the ship assignment to a specific loading/unloading berth according to the dynamic evolution of the port traffic: if one of the previously occupied berths frees up unexpectedly or earlier than expected (or, on the contrary, one berth is unexpectedly occupied), it is possible to re-assign another ship to it, provided that its authorization level is suitable. To this aim, different simulations have been performed, to test and validate the system flexibility to condition changes: Figure 3 depicts two different cases in which the blockchain node, during the simulation, sent a message with new authorization levels for a) two vehicles only and b) all the vehicles. In the first case, V3 had initially to avoid the pink areas, but then was allowed to cross even those. On the other hand, V4 started at the highest level but then had to avoid the second restricted pink area. The second simulation demonstrates how, even changing all the authorization levels together, the swarm is able to continue follow the leader, to avoid collisions and, in the meantime, to obey the restricted access rules. Note for example the exchange between V1 and V2: at first V2 is allowed to cross medium access areas (light blue), from which V1 is banned, and then the vehicles exchange their roles. Note that, thanks to the swarm ability to avoid collisions (obtained with a simple APF strategy),

this exchange occurs in a safe manner even if the robots cross each other's path.

The network aspects of the swarm (5 vehicle nodes plus 1 blockchain node) have been simulated with OMNeT++ (2022), an open-source C++ framework for event-driven network simulation. Figure 4 shows some frames of the case study in Figure 3(b). At the beginning of the simulation, the blockchain node sends to the leader vehicle all the authorization levels to be redistribute among the follower robots, and then, all the swarm agents start to follow their path. Suppose that all followers have on-board some sensor payload (possibly heterogeneous) to assess environment (e.g. port status (e.g. sampling pollutants in water after that big ships have performed their load/unload operations). All these measures should be processed by the blockchain node, in order to certify and make them unmodifiable. To this extent, followers continuously send their current measure (with a different timing, due to vehicle capability and sensor time-to-measure) to the leader robot, which is in charge of sending them to the blockchain node and require a certification transaction. At a certain point, during simulation, the blockchain requests a change in vehicle authorization levels (e.g. due to port operation or sampling needs); the followers receive from the leader their new role and continue to perform their sampling adhering to the new restrictions. As soon as the blockchain sends a stop message, the simulation ends. All the samples, executed paths and parameters are now certified by the blockchain. The same mechanism could be applied to allow third parties to change (through a defined procedure certified by the blockchain itself) the position of obstacles and/or their associated parameters during the simulation run. This would result in a highly dynamic environment, useful to estimate and assess actual robustness of the system versus abrupt environmental changes, and would allow to build up a updating trustable map of the current port situation. The blockchain would guarantee and certify the simulation results, without the possibility to alter or cherry-pick the cases with best system behaviours. A video reporting the simulation performed with OMNeT++ can be found here: https://shanghai-lectures.github.io/slides/IFAC_WC_2023_Blockchain.avi

6. DISCUSSION

As attractive as the scenario depicted above could be, there are a number of issues to cope with in order to be able to put it into practice. Some considerations can arise from these first test cases. On one hand, the blockchain latency issue is overcome by the adoption of the leader-follower approach: only the leader is in charge of managing blockchain transactions. This, further, allows to handle the scalability problem: the leader can communicate with a central operative station transmitting all the collected information and storing the transactions occurred; in this way the problem of having a blockchain exploding in size is solved. This approach mediates also the velocity issue: each robot is free to perform its own operations, while the leader vehicle is entirely devoted to manage the most time-demanding tasks related to blockchain transactions and certification procedures (besides this, it only has to follow the desired path). The behavior of complex

interconnected networks based on the blockchain is not well studied. Only a few pioneer researchers are active on this important new area of research, we would like to see more. However, there is significant activity in the field, workshops are organized, see for example Castello-Ferrer (2019); Gurcan and Bonsignorio (2020), one at IROS 2021 co-organized by one of the authors, special issues have been published on various journals, Castello-Ferrer et al. (2021); Bonsignorio and Gurcan (2021). Moreover, current existing blockchains on the proof-of-work concepts are comparatively slow and computing - and thus energy - intensive. Although there is steady progress in this area it may still take a few years before the situation become fully satisfactory. Significant progress has already occurred in the development of interconnection blockchains, such as Polkadot, allowing to connect different blockchain networks in a transparent and effective way. Ethereum blockchain has recently migrated to 'Proof-of-stake'.

7. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Our preliminary simulation results show that it is possible to manage effectively small swarms of surface autonomous vehicles by allocating the blockchain interfacing and role assignment functions on a subset of 'leading' vehicle and coordinating the rest of the connected surface vehicles by a swarm algorithm based on Belief Space Planning. From a general standpoint, we believe that a roadmap for the application of the blockchain technologies for the secure management of marine surface and underwater infrastructures like that described in this paper is necessary. As a community we should identify the priorities in the implementation of the different objectives and likely time and efforts needed to overcome the roadblocks. It is likely that cloud based centralized server based technologies will not scale to manage the smart marine infrastructure of the future - although it might be intuitive for many we plan to verify this in simulation in the future - and we will need to explore solutions based on distributed ledger technologies. Our future work include more detailed simulations and analysis of different blockchain implementations (in term of platforms and interaction logics implemented in the 'smart contracts') and real world testing of the most effective and efficient solutions.

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(a) Changing the authorization level of 2 followers: V3 from medium to high, V4 from high to low

(b) Changing the authorization level of all 4 followers: V1 from low to medium, V2 from medium to low, V3 from medium to high, V4 from high to low

Fig. 3. Path planned and executed by a swarm of 4 companion robots following 1 leader around a reference path crossing restricted areas. At a certain point, the blockchain sends a message to the leader, requesting a change in some or all the vehicle authorization levels. The leader sends the new role to each agent and the operations continue.

(a) The leader vehicle is propagating the initial authorization level for each vehicle, as received from the blockchain. Then, the robots start following the reference path/leader.

(b) The leader is sending samples collected by followers to the blockchain node requesting a certification transaction.

(c) The leader vehicle is receiving the new command with changing vehicles' authorization levels while the follower vehicle V3 is sending its current sample measurement

(d) The leader vehicle received a stop message from the blockchain and propagates it to follower vehicles

Fig. 4. Network behaviour during simulation of case study in Figure 3(b). Note that each follower vehicle has a different sample time, due to swarm heterogeneity, and thus the number of sent data messages is different for each of them.

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